

INNOVATION THROUGH TRADITION: PHARMACEUTICAL STANDARDIZATION OF *SUKHA PRASAVA NABHI LEPA* AND ITS TOPICAL PATCH

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ABSTRACT

The traditional Ayurvedic formulation *Sukha Prasava Nabhi Lepa* mentioned in *Yogaratanakara* under *Stri Garbha Rogadhikara* which is used to reduce labor pain. Although clinically effective, its application is less practiced due to the challenges associated with its traditional form, as its route of administration is *Nabhi* and its paste form does greasy and sticky. Adherence to these procedures has waned due to our fast-paced lifestyles. *Nabhi* is considered as center of gravitational force of the body and root of 24 *dhamanis* and 700 *siras*. This study explores a novel approach to reviving this unique therapy by adapting modern transdermal patch technology. Transforming the traditional *Lepa* into a transdermal patch allows its administration through the navel region, providing a simple, non-invasive, and patient-comfortable mode of delivery. This innovation aims to bridge classical wisdom with contemporary pharmaceutical

technology. This study includes Pharmaceutical study of *Sukhaprasava nabhi lepa* and its modification into topical patch by using different polymers with different trials which was assessed by physical parameters.

KEYWORDS: *Nabhi lepa*, *Sukha prasava nabhi lepa*, transdermal patch.

INTRODUCTION

Lepa Kalpana is indeed a unique preparation in Ayurveda, known for its quick pain-relieving properties. The analogy of extinguishing a fire by pouring water over a burning house illustrates its effectiveness in pacifying pain rapidly. One such approach involves using the skin as a medium to nourish the body and removes the toxins form the body.^[1] Across generations, traditions like applying *Hingu* in the periumbilical region of infants to soothe their cries and the practice of applying oil or *Ghritha* over it has been followed. Therefore, optimal drug absorption is often observed near the *Nabhi pradesha* (navel region) due to its significance as the root of 24 dhamanis^[2] (channels) and 700 *Siras* (vessels)^[3] resembling the intricate network of veins branching out like a tree's leaves.^[4] *Lepa* can have both systemic and localized effects, depending on the application site, whether it be *Sthanika* (specific) or *Sarvadaihika* (general). As *sukhaprasavanabhi lepa* observed to increase uterine contractions and reduce labour pain mainly contains Pippalimula, vacha and eranda taila mentioned by Yogaratnakara.^[5] This approach has to be revived in advanced way. Topical patches offer a non-invasive, self-administered solution, enhancing patient compliance while being cost-effective.^[6]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Review of literature

Nabhi (Umbelical region):

Nabhi is present in between *Amashaya* and *Pakvashaya*.^[7]

Anatomical point of view:

- *Nabhi* is taken as centre of gravitational force in body.^[8]
- *Acharya Sharangadhara* further elaborates that 24 *Dhamanis* (arterial channels) originate from the *Nabhi*: ten ascend, ten descend, and four run transversely, distributing *Rasa* and nourishment throughout the body.^[9]

CONTEMPROARY CORRELATION

The umbilicus, popularly known as the navel, is a median surface depression represented as a

remnant of the fetal end of the umbilical cord.^[11] It is composed of cicatricial tissue, a weak point of the anterior abdominal wall. The abdominal wall at the umbilical region is composed of skin, superficial fascia and more or less fat, three flat muscle of the anterior abdominal wall (external oblique, internal oblique & transverse abdominis), rectus abdominis, fascia transversalis, extraperitoneal connective tissue & peritoneum. It usually is situated at the level in between L3 & L4 vertebrae in adults but newborns little lower position.^[10]

Prasava Vignana

Ayurveda presents pregnancy (*garbhini avastha*) as a highly sensitive period requiring delicate management. *Vyana Vayu* initiates the contraction (*akshepa*) and relaxation (*prasarana*) of uterine muscles, stimulating *Apana Vayu* to expel the fetus from the uterus. *Acharya Charaka* refers to this integrated function as *Prasutimaruta*—the vital force of labor.^[11]

To facilitate *Sukhaprasava* (easy and complication-free delivery), classical text *Yogaratanakara* recommend external applications such as *Sukhaprasavakara Lepa* on the *Nabhi* (navel). This herbal paste, known for its *snigdha* quality, is believed to soften tissues, reduce dryness (*rukshata*) of *Vata*, and promote ligament flexibility, thereby supporting uterine contractions and fetal expulsion.

Drug Review

Table showing the family and botanical name of raw drugs

Drug	Latin name	Family	Useful part
<i>Pippali mula</i>	<i>Pippali longum L.</i>	<i>Piperaceae</i>	Root
<i>Vacha</i>	<i>Acorus calamus L.</i>	<i>Araceae</i>	Rhizome
<i>Eranda taila</i>	<i>Ricinis communis</i>	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	Seeds

Sukhaprasava Nabhi lepa contains herbs like *Pippalimula* (*Piper longum*) and *Vacha* (*Acorus calamus*), *Eranda taila* known for their analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties, could be integrated into these patches to provide targeted relief. The localized application on the umbilicus, which is rich in vascular and neural connections, supports efficient transdermal absorption and systemic action.

Transdermal Drug Delivery System (TDDS)^[12]

It is an advanced method of drug administration that enables the transport of therapeutic agents through the skin and into systemic circulation. This route eliminates the need for the

gastrointestinal tract and avoids hepatic first-pass metabolism, which can otherwise reduce a drug's bioavailability.

Basic Components of a Transdermal Drug Delivery System

1. Polymer Matrix or Drug Reservoir

The polymer matrix is produced by dispersing the drug in a polymer base, either in solid or liquid form. The selected polymer must be biocompatible and chemically stable with other formulation components.

Classification of Polymers

- Natural Polymers: Zein, gelatin, waxes, gums, natural rubber, cellulose derivatives, etc.
- Synthetic Elastomers: Polybutadiene, butyl rubber, silicone rubber, polyisobutylene, acrylonitrile, neoprene, etc.
- Synthetic Polymers: Polyurea, polyvinyl alcohol, polyvinyl chloride, polyethylene, polypropylene, polyacrylate, polyamide, etc.

1. Drug

Ideal drug candidates for TDDS should meet the following criteria

Require a low daily dose (generally less than 20 mg/day).

2. Permeation Enhancers

Permeation enhancers are agents that temporarily increase the permeability of the stratum corneum, allowing the drug to reach therapeutic concentrations in systemic circulation. They act by altering the structure of lipids within the skin barrier.

3. Backing Laminate

The backing laminate acts as a supportive and protective layer that prevents the loss of drug or permeation enhancers through the non-skin surface. It must be impermeable and chemically compatible with the drug and other excipients.

Examples: Vinyl, polyethylene, polyester films, and metallic plastic laminates

4. Plasticizers and Solvents

Plasticizers enhance the flexibility of the polymer matrix and reduce brittleness, while solvents assist in dissolving or uniformly dispersing the drug and excipients within the patch.

Examples of Plasticizers: Glycerol, polyethylene glycol, propylene glycol.

Examples of Solvents: Chloroform, methanol, acetone, isopropanol,

METHODOLOGY

The Classical method of *Lepa kalpana* was followed for the SPNL preparation and for the topical patch following contemporary research papers and journals.

This study includes

1. Preparation of *Sukhaprasava nabhi lepa*
2. Preparation of *Sukhaprasava nabhi lepa* topical patch (SPNL topical patch)

Practical number 1 – Preparation of *sukha prasava nabhi lepa*^[13]

Raw drug for preparation of formulation was collected from known sources, identified by experts of department of *dravyaguna* and analysed in QC laboratory, Muniyal Institute Of Ayurveda Medical Sciences (MIAMS).

Method of preparation

- Equal quantity of *vacha* and *pippali mula churna* was taken in a clean *khalva yantra*.
- Pre measured *eranda taila* followed by water was added accordingly to get proper consistency of paste, later quantity of *drava dravya* used for the preparation of *lepa* was noted.
- Finally quantity of paste obtained is taken and measured.
- Result: SPNL quantity obtained was 95gm.

Drug	Ratios	Quantity taken
(a)Pippalimula	1 part	25gm
(b)Vacha	1 part	25gm
(c)Eranda taila	1/4 th	5ml w/v
Water	Q.S	40ml w/v

(a)

(b)

(c)

Practical number 2 – Preparation of SPNL topical patch

Step 1 Extraction of SPNL churna

For transdermal patch bases, the selection of an appropriate extraction method plays a essential in maximizing both the yield and the quality of active phytoconstituents from raw materials. Extraction is the first step which was tried with the following different methods.

1. Decoction: Heating of coarse powder with specified ratio of water to extract water-soluble constituents.

2. Soxhlet extraction: Using organic solvents to obtain lipophilic compounds.

Soxhlets method was selected for the final patch as extract obtained was more in this method and formulation contain lipid which is suitable for the experiment

Soxhlets extraction Method

- Weighed SPNL churna filled in Soxhlet thimble which is wrapped with in whatman filter paper and Fill the round bottom flask with measured solvent
- Insert the thimble containing sample into extractor and attach the condenser on the top and connected with water inlet and outlet for cooling.
- Heated the flask using a heating mantle and Final solvent was evaporated in water bath
- Final extract was measured in weighing balance.

SPNL Extraction	SPNL Churna (Qt)	Castor Oil	Ethanol (Qt)	Duration	Extract Weight
Batch 1	50gm	1 ml	200ml	7hours	9.68gm
Batch 2	50gm	1ml	200ml	7hours	9.71gm

Step 3: Preparation of Patch by solvent casting method^[14]

Preparation of SPNLTP was done by 3 batches named Batch-1, Batch-2, Batch-3, Each batch contains 3 samples named A,B,C.

Method: Solvent casting method

Step 1: Preparation of Polymer Solution

Sodium alginate was weighed and dissolved in a solvent mixture of ethanol and deionized water. The solution was stirred continuously using a glass rod under water bath to get clear and uniform solution.

Step 2: Addition of Plasticizer

Glycerol was added to the polymer solution as a plasticizer and mixed thoroughly.

Step 3: Incorporation of Herbal Extract

The pre-prepared SPNL churna extract was added gradually to the polymer-plasticizer solution under continuous stirring to obtain a homogenous drug-polymer matrix.

Step 4: Casting and Drying

The final formulation was cast onto clean, levelled petri dishes and dried in hot air oven for 6 hours to facilitate solvent evaporation.

Step 5: Removal and Cutting

After complete drying, the patches were carefully removed and cut into uniform sizes. The patches were stored in airtight zip lock cover under room temperature.

Polymer Screening and Optimization

An initial screening was carried out using a variety of natural and semi-synthetic polymers to identify the most suitable film-forming agent for the transdermal herbal patch. The polymers evaluated included pectin, xanthan gum, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), gum acacia (gum acanthum), polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP), and sodium alginate. Each polymer was individually formulated using the solvent casting method with fixed concentrations of glycerol as the plasticizer and extract as the active herbal component.

Trial 1. Sodium alginate

Trial 2. Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose

Trial 3. Xanthum

Trial 5. Pectin

Trial 6. Gum acanthum

Trial 7. PVP

Polymers	Extract quantity	Polymer quantity	Distilled water	Duration
Trial 1	0.5 gm	0.5gm	25ml	20min
Trial 2	0.5 gm	0.5gm	20ml	26min
Trial 3	0.5 gm	0.5gm	30ml	30min
Trial 4	0.5 gm	0.5gm	15ml	18min
Trial 5	0.5 gm	0.5gm	40ml	30min
Trial 6	0.5 gm	0.5gm	20ml	35min
Trial 7	0.5 gm	0.5gm	30ml	40min

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Observation of Physical parameters showing the trial batch samples

Trial	Clumping	Color	Appearance	Elasticity	Spread ability
Trial 1	Absent	Brown	Opaque	Present	Present
Trial 2	Present	Honey	Semi Opaque	Present	Present
Trial 3	Absent	White	Transparent	Present	Absent
Trial 4	Present	Wood	Sticky	Present	Present
Trial 5	Absent	Light yellow	Crystalline	Absent	Absent
Trial 6	Absent	brown	Semi opaque	Cracking	absent
Trial 7	Absent	honey	Opaque	Cracking	absent

Trial 1

Trial 2

Trial 3

Trial 4

Trial 5

Trial 6

Trial 7

SPNL Batch ABC

Soxhlet's apparatus

Sodium alginate was selected as the primary polymer for the formulation of transdermal patches due to its satisfactory performance in all evaluation criteria including organoleptic character.

Sukha prasava nabhilepa transdermal patch (SPNLTP) was prepared in 3 batch, each batch contains 3 samples by following SOP.

Ingredients and ratios

SPNLTP	Polymer	SPNL extract	ethanol	Distilled water	Glycerol
Batch 1	0.5gm	0.8gm	5ml	25ml	2drops
Batch 2	0.5gm	0.8gm	5ml	25ml	2 drops
Batch 3	0.5gm	0.8gm	5ml	25ml	2drops

DISCUSSION

Classical method of preparation of Lepa mentioned by Acharya sharangadhara was followed to prepare SPNL.

Classical texts specify the thickness of a *Vathaghna Lepa* as approximately 1/4th Angula (~4 mm), reflecting the optimal amount required for proper absorption and action. this is taken as standard parameter.

The quantity of Sneha Dravya (unctuous base) is not mentioned in classical formulations. However, traditional principles recommend using one-fourth the quantity of the drug in case of *vatahara* action which ensures appropriate therapeutic effect. Deviations in the proportion of Sneha may alter the pharmacological action and absorption of the active constituents.

In the modification of *Lepa Kalpana* into herbal transdermal patches, polymers and emulsifying agents play a crucial role in drug stabilization, controlled release, mechanical integrity, and adhesion. Both natural and synthetic polymers are employed to optimize patch performance and ensure reproducible therapeutic effects.

Natural polymers like Sodium alginate, xanthum gum and Gum Acacia and pectin were used in this study. Synthetic polymers like HPMC, PVP are also used.

Some polymers are hydrophilic and some are lipophilic. selecting the proper polymer base is the crucial part. It is checked by physicochemical evaluation like texture, elongation.

For transdermal patch bases, the selection of an appropriate extraction method plays a critical role in maximizing both the yield and the quality of active phytoconstituents from raw materials. Optimizing extraction not only enhances the therapeutic efficacy of the final product but also minimizes the time and cost.

For preparing the patch, extraction is the first step which was tried with the different methods i.e. Decoction where coarse powder with specified ratio of water to extract water-soluble

constituents and other method is Soxhlet extraction by using organic solvents to obtain lipophilic compounds.

Soxhlets method was selected for the final patch as extract obtained was more in this method and formulation contain lipid which is suitable for the experiment.

For preparation of SPNLTP Solvent casting method is used. An initial screening was carried by different trials using a variety of natural and semi-synthetic polymers to identify the most suitable film-forming agent for the transdermal herbal patch. The polymers evaluated included pectin, xanthan gum, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), gum acacia (gum acanthum), polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP), and sodium alginate.

All *formulations* were assessed based on predefined criteria: clumping tendency, color uniformity, overall appearance, elasticity, and spreadability. Among the polymers tested, sodium alginate demonstrated superior film-forming properties with a smooth, uniform appearance, good elasticity, and excellent spreadability, without any evidence of clumping or phase separation. Hence, sodium alginate was selected as the optimized polymer for the development of the final transdermal patch.

Optimization of Polymer Ratio

Several *formulation* trials were conducted using varying concentrations of sodium alginate to optimize the physicochemical properties of the transdermal patch. The polymer-to-solvent ratio and the concentration of plasticizer were systematically varied in each trial. Each *formulation* was evaluated for film-forming capacity, flexibility, homogeneity, drying time, and ease of removal.

Sodium alginate was selected as the primary polymer for the *formulation* of transdermal patches due to its satisfactory performance in all evaluation criteria including organoleptic character.

CONCLUSION

In the current era, traditional methods may be underutilized due to inconvenience or lack of familiarity. Therefore, reimagining *Nabhi Lepa* in the form of a transdermal patch offers a practical, standardized, and patient-compliant alternative.

In converting *Lepa* into a topical patch, traditional guidelines like thickness according to doshas, serve as a foundation for standardization parameters, such as patch thickness, drug load, adhesive properties, and release rate in patch. Maintaining these parameters ensures that the herbal patch preserves the efficacy of the classical formulation.

The umbilical region (*Nabhi*), identified in *Ayurveda* as a vital energetic and anatomical center, offers a promising site for transdermal delivery. Its rich vascular and neural connectivity supports the concept of effective systemic absorption through localized application.

The use of the Soxhlet extraction method ensured efficient extraction of both hydrophilic and lipophilic constituents, providing a concentrated and reproducible yield of active phytochemicals from *pippali mula, vacha and eranda taila*.

From a pharmaceutical perspective, multiple polymers—sodium alginate, xanthan gum, gum acacia, PVP, and pectin—were evaluated to identify an optimal matrix for patch formulation. Sodium alginate was selected based on superior film-forming capacity, flexibility, and stability.

Nabhi lepa is clinically less practiced but having high therapeutic effect. An attempt was made to revive the unique route of administration.

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